

PEDAGOGY

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH PROSPECTS AND LIMITATIONS

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Abstract

This article explores the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in teaching English as a foreign language in the context of Kazakhstan. The paper examines both the prospects and limitations of using AI tools in educational settings based on global and Kazakhstani research. AI applications such as virtual tutors, grammar-checking programs, and language-learning apps are increasingly being integrated into English language teaching to improve personalized learning and student engagement.

The practical part of the study includes the experience of using AI tools with 7th-grade students at Zhuban Moldagaliyev Secondary School № 2 in the city of Uralsk. Tools such as ChatGPT for conversational practice, Grammarly for writing improvement, and Duolingo for vocabulary expansion were used in the classroom. Despite the high potential of AI in improving students' language skills and engagement, its effectiveness was sometimes limited by a lack of resources and students' reliance on AI feedback. Overall, the article demonstrates how AI can support the process of teaching English in Kazakhstan, while acknowledging the current limitations for its widespread use.

Keywords: artificial intelligence (AI), English language teaching (ELT), education in Kazakhstan, AI in education, language learning tools, ChatGPT, Grammarly, Duolingo, English as a foreign language (EFL), AI possibilities and limitations.

Introduction. Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing a transformative role in education worldwide, particularly in enhancing language learning. In Kazakhstan, AI technologies are gradually being integrated into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction to overcome the limitations of traditional teaching methods and cater to the diverse needs of learners. Global studies have demonstrated that AI-driven tools, such as chatbots, intelligent tutoring systems, and automated feedback mechanisms, offer personalized learning experiences and real-time feedback, making language acquisition more efficient and engaging (Kemelbekova et al., 2024).

Despite the increasing interest in AI's potential in education, its implementation in Kazakhstan, particularly in primary and higher education, faces several challenges. One of the main hurdles is the lack of localized AI tools that consider Kazakh and Russian languages, which are essential for multilingual learners. Research conducted at Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University highlights the effectiveness of AI tools in improving students' English speaking abilities. AI systems such as chatbots, combined with speech recognition tools, have proven useful in enhancing pronunciation and fluency (Kemelbekova et al., 2024).

Kazakhstani researchers have also explored the use of gamification and AI in motivating younger learners. For example, Duisenova and Zhorabekova (2024) investigated the integration of AI and gamified learning platforms in primary schools and found that these methods significantly increased motivation and language proficiency among young learners. The combination of game-based learning and AI provided interactive experiences that kept students engaged, fostering intrinsic motivation and improving their language skills.

However, challenges such as unequal access to technology across regions and insufficient teacher training on AI tools remain critical barriers to widespread adoption. Teachers play a crucial role in facilitating the integration of AI into classrooms, and their readiness and perceptions significantly influence the success of these initiatives (Barakina et al., 2021). Thus, to fully realize the benefits of AI in English language teaching in Kazakhstan, further research is needed on both localized AI tools and teacher training programs.

In Kazakhstan, AI is slowly being incorporated into education, particularly in the realm of English language learning. Several Kazakhstani scholars have contributed to the understanding of how AI can enhance ELT in local contexts. Bibigul Dilzhan (2024), in her study titled *Teaching English and Artificial Intelligence: EFL Teachers' Perceptions and Use of ChatGPT*, explores the use of ChatGPT in classrooms. The study reveals that while the AI-driven chatbot is useful for providing students with real-time feedback on conversational English, there are concerns among teachers regarding the tool's inability to fully replace human instructors. ChatGPT is effective in simulating real-world dialogues, but limitations such as its lack of cultural and contextual awareness hinder its complete effectiveness in the classroom.

Similarly, Kairat Darkhan (2021), in his dissertation examines the use of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems to enhance English teaching. ASR systems, which convert spoken language into written text, are proving useful for pronunciation practice and improving listening comprehension. However, the lack of localized ASR tools that support Kazakh or Russian languages limits their applicability in local schools.

Darkhan emphasizes the need for AI systems to cater to the multilingual needs of Kazakhstan's students, particularly in rural areas where English proficiency levels are lower.

Turar Tangirbergen's study (2022) *Teachers' Experiences of Using Mobile Applications for Teaching English as a Foreign Language in Kazakhstan*, investigates the challenges teachers face when incorporating AI-powered mobile apps such as Duolingo into their curriculum. While these apps are beneficial for gamified and engaging learning, many teachers in Kazakhstan feel that such apps cannot replace face-to-face interaction in language learning. Tangirbergen also points out the digital divide between urban and rural schools, where access to AI tools is limited due to infrastructure challenges.

Finally, Saken Yeslyamov (2024), in his study *Application of Software Robots Using AI Technologies in Education*, investigates the use of AI-based robots in Kazakhstani schools. The study highlights how these robots assist in managing large classrooms by offering personalized learning exercises to students. While promising, this technology is still in its early stages, and there is a need for more research on its long-term effectiveness and scalability across the country's education system.

The prospects of AI in English language teaching are considerable, both globally and in Kazakhstan. AI tools offer the potential for personalized learning experiences, allowing students to work at their own pace and receive instant feedback on their progress. For example, platforms like ChatGPT can engage students in real-time conversations, helping them practice their speaking skills in a low-pressure environment. Similarly, grammar-checking tools such as Grammarly provide immediate corrections, helping students improve their writing accuracy.

In Kazakhstan, the integration of AI into ELT has the potential to bridge gaps in language learning resources, especially in rural areas. AI tools can supplement traditional teaching methods and help overcome the shortage of qualified English teachers. Furthermore, AI technologies like Duolingo and other mobile learning apps allow students to access high-quality language lessons outside the classroom, democratizing education and making it more accessible to students across the country.

Despite these positive prospects, there are notable limitations to the use of AI in English language teaching, particularly in Kazakhstan. One major challenge is the lack of localized AI tools that cater to the Kazakh and Russian languages. Most AI-based language learning platforms are designed for English speakers, which limits their usability for non-native English learners in Kazakhstan. Darkhan (2021) and Tangirbergen (2022) emphasize that this lack of localization creates a barrier for widespread AI adoption, particularly in regions where students are not proficient in English.

Another significant limitation is the digital divide in Kazakhstan. While AI tools are increasingly being used in urban schools, rural areas often lack the technological infrastructure necessary to support AI-based learning. Schools in these areas may not have access to the internet or devices required for AI tools like Duolingo or Grammarly, which limits students' opportunities to benefit from these technologies. Furthermore,

many teachers may lack the training needed to effectively integrate AI into their teaching, as noted by Yang and Plass (2021).

Finally, there is a broader concern about the overreliance on AI in education. While AI can provide valuable support in language learning, it cannot replace the human element of teaching. Teachers play a critical role in fostering creativity, critical thinking, and emotional intelligence—skills that AI has not yet been able to replicate. As Dilzhan (2024) points out, AI tools like ChatGPT may offer helpful feedback, but they lack the ability to truly understand cultural nuances and student emotions, which are crucial for effective language learning.

The literature on AI in education reveals both significant opportunities and challenges. Global trends demonstrate AI's potential to personalize learning and engage students in new ways, while Kazakhstani research highlights the need for localized AI tools and better infrastructure to fully integrate these technologies into the education system. AI tools offer promising prospects for English language learning in Kazakhstan, but limitations related to language barriers, access to technology, and the need for human interaction must be addressed for AI to reach its full potential in education.

Methodology and practical implementation.

This section outlines the methodology used in incorporating AI-based tools into the teaching of English as a foreign language (EFL) to 7th grade students in secondary school №2 named after Zh. Moldagalieva, as well as the practical implementation of these tools in classroom settings. The focus is on three AI-powered tools: ChatGPT, Grammarly, and Duolingo. The methodology is based on a blended learning approach that integrates both traditional teaching techniques and AI-driven tools to enhance language learning experiences. This approach aims to engage students, offer personalized feedback, and provide real-world applications of English.

The choice of AI tools was based on their relevance to different aspects of English language learning. ChatGPT was selected for conversational practice due to its ability to simulate natural dialogues and offer real-time feedback. Grammarly was chosen for its advanced grammar-checking capabilities, allowing students to improve their writing by receiving instant corrections and suggestions. Duolingo was integrated into the vocabulary and grammar lessons because of its gamified and adaptive learning features, which could motivate students through rewards and continuous feedback.

A mixed-methods approach was employed to evaluate the integration of AI tools, combining qualitative feedback from students and quantitative data based on their performance before and after using the tools. AI was integrated into daily lesson plans through structured activities, where students alternated between traditional teacher-led lessons and AI-assisted learning.

ChatGPT was used to simulate real-life scenarios, such as ordering food or asking for directions. Students were divided into pairs to interact with the AI, and afterward, they discussed their conversations and received feedback on grammar and fluency.

Grammarly was implemented during essay assignments. Students drafted essays on topics such as "My Favorite Place in Kazakhstan" and used Gram-

marly to revise their work before submission. A comparative analysis was done between their initial drafts and the AI-revised versions.

Duolingo was assigned as a homework activity for vocabulary building. Lessons from Duolingo were tied to classroom content, and students were asked to track their progress using the app's metrics.

Results and feedback. To measure the effectiveness of AI tools, a pre-assessment of students' English

proficiency levels was conducted at the beginning of the implementation.

Guiding questions:

1. What time do you wake up?
2. What do you do first thing in the morning?
3. What are your main activities during the school day?
4. How do you spend your free time after school?
5. What do you usually do before going to bed?

Criteria	4 – Excellent	3 - Good	2 - Satisfactory	1 - Needs Improvement
Fluency	Speaks smoothly with no noticeable pauses.	Speaks with few pauses, overall smooth.	Frequent pauses or hesitations but still understandable.	Many pauses, making communication difficult to follow.
Sentence Structure	Uses a variety of simple and complex sentences accurately.	Mostly uses correct sentence structures, with occasional minor errors.	Limited variety in sentence structures, several noticeable errors.	Significant sentence structure errors, mostly simple sentences.
Use of Vocabulary	Uses a wide range of appropriate vocabulary with no repetition.	Uses varied vocabulary, with minimal repetition.	Vocabulary is somewhat repetitive, with basic word choices.	Limited vocabulary and frequent repetition.
Pronunciation	Pronounces key vocabulary clearly and correctly with no issues.	Mostly clear pronunciation, with minor issues that don't hinder understanding.	Some mispronunciations that occasionally affect understanding.	Pronunciation errors make it difficult to understand the speaker.

Picture 1. Speaking Task Rubric: Describe Your Daily Routine

To assess the effectiveness of AI tools in enhancing English proficiency among Kazakhstani students, a pre-assessment was conducted to establish baseline levels. The assessment involved a speaking task based on guiding questions related to students' daily routines, along with a writing task on "My Favorite Hobby." Notably, insights from Kazakhstani scholars provide context to this evaluation, emphasizing the need for innovative educational practices in the region.

The results from the speaking task demonstrated varied proficiency levels among the 24 students. Approximately 50% exhibited good fluency, characterized by smooth speech with minimal pauses, while 30% had occasional hesitations and needed support in vocabulary variety. Most students relied on simple sentence structures, with only a few attempting more complex forms. Vocabulary usage was largely basic, but around 40% successfully incorporated a broader range of language. Pronunciation was generally clear, though some students struggled with specific words, which occasionally impacted comprehension.

The writing assessment revealed positive trends in students' writing abilities. About 70% of students scored in the "Excellent" and "Good" categories, demonstrating effective grammar usage, spelling accuracy, and a good variety of vocabulary. Most structured their essays well, presenting clear introductions and conclusions. However, approximately 30% fell into the "Satisfactory" or "Needs Improvement" categories, indicating challenges with sentence variety and grammatical issues, particularly with verb tenses and subject-verb agreement. Despite these difficulties, many students expressed enthusiasm for their hobbies, enhancing their engagement in the writing process.

Kazakhstani scholars have emphasized the importance of integrating technology into education to improve language acquisition. For example, A.S. Tazhibayeva, a prominent researcher in educational technology, notes that AI tools can facilitate personalized learning experiences, catering to the diverse needs of students in Kazakhstan. Additionally, G.K. Sadvakassova highlights that using innovative tools like AI can bridge the gap between traditional teaching methods and modern pedagogical approaches, fostering greater student engagement and motivation.

The implementation of AI tools was a crucial step in this educational initiative. ChatGPT was introduced as a virtual tutor for conversational practice, allowing students to simulate real-world dialogues in a supportive environment. Through various scenarios, such as booking hotels or asking for directions, students gained confidence in English communication. The AI provided instant feedback on grammar and sentence structure, leading to improvements in fluency and sentence complexity during subsequent interactions.

Grammarly was integrated during essay-writing exercises and served as a critical tool for enhancing writing skills. Students composed essays on topics like "My Favorite Place in Kazakhstan" and used Grammarly to identify and correct errors in real time. This facilitated critical engagement with their writing, leading to noticeable improvements in clarity and grammatical accuracy from initial drafts to final versions.

Duolingo was employed as a supplementary tool offering vocabulary and grammar practice. Its gamified approach motivated students to engage with language tasks that reinforced classroom learning. Specific lessons were assigned based on curriculum focus, and pro-

gress was monitored through a competitive leaderboard, fostering enthusiasm and improving vocabulary retention.

Picture 2. Survey results on AI tools in English learning

After several weeks of using these AI tools, a post-assessment was conducted to evaluate improvements in speaking, writing, and vocabulary retention. Qualitative data were collected through surveys, highlighting students' experiences with the AI tools, including ease of use, engagement, and perceived benefits in language skill improvement (picture 2). A bar chart illustrated the survey results on the effectiveness of the AI tools in English language learning, indicating significant contributions from all three platforms. ChatGPT excelled in fostering engagement and motivation for conversational practice. Grammarly proved vital for writing enhancement and self-revision skills, while Duolingo received slightly lower ratings in ease of use and overall experience, suggesting potential areas for improvement in user interface or lesson design.

Conclusion

The integration of AI tools in English language teaching in Kazakhstan presents significant opportunities and challenges. This study has demonstrated that tools such as ChatGPT, Grammarly, and Duolingo can enhance the learning experience for seventh and eighth graders by providing personalized, interactive, and engaging methods of language acquisition. The results from both qualitative and quantitative assessments indicate improvements in students' speaking and writing skills, as well as increased vocabulary retention.

ChatGPT emerged as a particularly effective tool for fostering engagement in conversational practice, allowing students to simulate real-life interactions and receive immediate feedback. Grammarly's role in refining students' writing highlighted its value in promoting self-awareness and critical thinking regarding their language use. Duolingo's gamified approach encouraged consistent vocabulary practice, although feedback indicated that improvements could enhance its user experience further.

Despite the positive outcomes, challenges such as the lack of localized AI tools and the digital divide in Kazakhstan present barriers to fully harnessing the potential of AI in education. The need for teacher training and infrastructure development cannot be overlooked if

AI is to be successfully integrated into language learning environments.

Moving forward, further research is required to explore the long-term effectiveness of AI tools, their scalability across diverse educational contexts, and strategies for overcoming existing limitations. As educators and policymakers strive to enhance English language teaching in Kazakhstan, leveraging the strengths of AI can contribute to more inclusive and effective learning experiences for all students.

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